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Two 18th century Guaraní devotional manuscripts. From the Jesuit missions in Paraguay through Guaraní families to Wilhelm von Humboldt.

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Abstract

In this article, we present two Guaraní manuscripts in the Staatsbibliothek Berlin, Manuscript amer. 12, and Manuscript amer. 13, now in possession of the Biblioteka Jagiellońska in Krakow, Polonia. The two manuscripts have been in the 19th century in the collection of Ignaz Franz W. M von Olfers (1793-1871), ambassador to Brazil 1826-1828, bought in Brazil at the request of Wilhelm von Humboldt, a friend of Olfers for his linguistic studies. They are both devotional manuscripts, the first one a version of Explicacion de el catecismo, by Nicolás Yapuguay, printed in the Paraguayan Jesuit reducciones (missions) in 1724 with some devotional exercises of daily mental prayers added. The second manuscript is a compilation of various texts, a Guaraní translation of a Catecismo, by Gerónimo de Ripalda, as we see comparing this version with a manuscript in the British Library. Added to this part we find a translation of some José de Acosta sermons from the Tercero catecismo y exposicion de la Doctrina Christiana, por Sermones ... Los Reyes [i.e., Lima]: by the printer Antonio Ricardo, 1585, and another part of Sermons, by unknown authors (one “Padre Anselmo” is mentioned in a marginal note). These manuscripts have been conserved on place, as they have been in use even in post-jesuitical times, in one manuscript we have the mention of an Indigenous: Izidro Taropé // Mestre da musica and the Mission Santo Ângelo, today in Brazil, Rio Grande do Sul. We shortly present these manuscripts as important sources for devotional education probably among the members of Cofradías (congregations).

Introduction

In this contribution, we present a brief philological description of two hitherto neglected manuscripts from the Jesuit reducciones in South America in the 18th century. These manuscripts can be seen as an important document for the devotional practices in the missions and their provenance history shows for which reasons they found interest by collectors and researchers in the 19th century. There is indirect evidence that probably Wilhelm von Humboldt had knowledge of them, even if he didn't mention them in his linguistic works.

Presentation

These manuscripts are part of the collection of the Staatsbibliothek Berlin, this part of the collection is now, due to WWII, in the possession of the Biblioteka Jagiellońska in Krakow, Polonia.

They are not dated but from what we know about the Jesuit manuscripts from the Paraguay missions, known as reducciones, they are certainly written in the first decades of the 18th century. As they also contain in one part a version of a Catecism, dated in another manuscript 1716 (see below) this is very probable. The bindings are in both cases 19th century style with marmorized paper and the stamps of the Berlin library (Königliche Bibliothek at that time). Most probably, the binding was made at the moment the library acquired the manuscript in 1897.

Many manuscripts from the reducciones are now in poor material conditions and usually these manuscripts had no bindings at all, or they were damaged by continual use. The two manuscripts in Berlin were bought by the Berlin library together with the *Arte* (a linguistic work of Pablo Restivo, 1724) and the Vocabulary printed in the missions themselves and two medieval manuscripts not related to their topic.¹

In the annex, we give a more detailed description of the hybrid status of the two manuscripts composed by various types of religious texts genres at that time.²

¹ The prints: *Vocabulario de la lengua Guaraní* (Libri impr. rari qu. 314), acquisition number 1897.8245, January 28. 1898, the *Arte de la lengua Guaraní von 1724* (Libri impr. Rari qu.315), both also now also in Krakow, Polonia. For the Jesuit presses in the missions, all extant copies and their provenances see Obermeier 2019b. Today we find a digital version of most of the early Guaraní prints by Jesuits in a John Carter Brown library copy in the Indigenous language collection of this library, also on archive.org.

² Linguistic description in: Cerno, Leonardo, Brignon, Thomas, Los "Manuscripta americana" 12 y 13. Pistas textuales, intertextuales y contextuales para la caracterización de dos manuscritos guaraníes, in: *Bibliothek und Wissenschaft* 53.2020, Sonderheft Manuscripta

For practical reasons we are citing the original Manuscript amer. 12, as B1, Manuscript amer. 13 as B2.³

The 19th century provenance

First some important remarks about the 19th century provenance. We will treat some early Guaraní owners later. The two manuscripts have been in the collection of Ignaz Franz W. M von Olfers (1793-1871), ambassador to Brazil 1826-1828, bought probably at the request of Wilhelm von Humboldt, a friend of Olfers (see below). Owned by the Olfers family until 1897, they were conserved in the family manor Methgethen Castle, East Prussia at that time, today part of Russia. Acquisition of the Royal Library of Berlin 1897 through the Königsberg based antiquarian William Koch together with the Jesuit prints mentioned above and two unrelated religious manuscripts from the Middle Ages. Königsberg is also in East Prussia, so the family relied on a local antiquarian, probably of their acquaintance.

Their owner Olfers entered a diplomatic career after having studied medicine and natural sciences in Göttingen and Berlin (thesis Berlin 1816). Between 1816-1820 he was legation secretary of the Prussian embassy in Rio de Janeiro. Later promoted to Legationsrat (legation councilor), he served in Lisbon and Naples. He returned to Brazil when the young country was recognized by Prussia in 1826 as an ambassador to work in the embassy between 1826-1828. Later back in Berlin he became director general of the Royal museums.

The two manuscripts are devotional literature, not only sermon collection, in Spanish sermonario or also when referring to certain saints usually known in Spanish as sanctuario-sanctuary.

In our study, we cannot enter in detail as to the sermons contained in the B2 manuscript. The themes and texts of the sermons (with the exception of the Acosta part sermons) are very similar to those of Yapuguay, Sermones, printed in the reducciones in 1727, but the texts are diverse. Research about manuscript sermons from the Jesuit missions in Paraguay (including territory in what is now Argentina) is still at a beginning.⁴

Manuscript B1 is containing the Explication de el Catecism, printed in the reducciones in 1724 also with the authorship of the indigenous Nicolás Yapuguay. In B2, we find a combination of texts not common in the extant sermonaries, even if the combination of sermons with other genres is not

americana, *Indigene Handschriften aus Mittel- und Südamerika in Berlin und Krakau* (16.–19. Jh.). *Indigenous manuscripts from Middle and South America in Berlin and Krakow* (16th to 19th c), ed. by Angelika Danielewski, pp.79-120.

³ Digital versions cited in the annex.

⁴ For a study about the terminology used in religious education, see: Otazú Melgarejo 2006.

unique.⁵ Can the Berlin B2 manuscript still be called a sermonary? It is a collectanea of various devotional text types. It is easy to describe B1 (Amer.12) and give an idea about its use. The Explanation by Yapuguay, published in the Jesuit presses under Jesuit control is a basic text for religious education in the Paraguayan Jesuit missions, probably mainly used in congregations. Another hand added some prayers, as we will mention below in our description.

The second manuscript B2 is more complicated. B2 is a combination of a catechism in the first part with sermons, more precisely two different sermonary types, maybe separate before binding (or even there have been three booklets with sermons as there is a provenance note and some blancs, in what we called the “III. Part” in our description, see below). The first text is a traditional catechism. The Spanish text of the questions corresponds to those of most renowned version by Antonio Ruiz de Montoya (published in Madrid 1640) but it is a Guaraní version of another Spanish catechism, only extant in manuscript form, as we know from the comparison with a catechism manuscript collection in Guaraní now in the British library.⁶ This London version is described in the title page as Francisco Martinez's translation of the Ripalda catechism into Guaraní. Another hand has added in the Berlin B2 manuscript the Creed in Guaraní at the end.

Then a first part of Sermons follows, written by the Jesuit José de Acosta (1540-1600), the topics, the order and numbering corresponds to those of the Tercero catecismo y exposicion de la Doctrina Christiana, por Sermones ... Los Reyes [i.e., Lima]: by the printer Antonio Ricardo, 1585, in B2 in a Guaraní translation for use in the Paraguayan reducciones. Acosta's name is also mentioned in a marginal note at the beginning. As the importance of the Lima council for religious education in South American indigenous languages is known, we don't have to enter in details to explain the reason for choosing Acostas trilingual catechism in Spanish, Aymara and Quechua written on behalf of the Lima council as an accepted model.⁷ Another hand has joined in the Berlin manuscript two

⁵ We are working on a description of all extant sermones manuscripts in Guaraní: *La literatura religiosa de las reducciones jesuíticas rioplatenses. Los Sermonarios rioplatenses manuscritos y los libros de devoción particular. Estudios preliminares a una investigación sobre Teología-lingüística- bibliografía*, draft 2025.

⁶ BL Add 21262, published together with other Catechism from this manuscript as *Catecismos vários*, São Paulo: Univ. de São Paulo, Fac. de Filosofia, Ciências e Letras, Boletim, 6 vol. 1952-56 as nr. 24.1952; 27.1953; 29.1954; 30.1956 and 32.1956 of the serial *Etnografia e tupi-guarani* in the Boletim, ed by the Universidade de São Paulo, Faculdade de filosofia, ciências e letras. The Ripalda as vol 3, with the title *Catecismo y exposicion breve de la doctrina christiana por el P. M. G. de Ripalda; emendado y traducido en guarani por Francisco Martinez*, São Paulo: Universidade de São Paulo, 1954.

⁷ We only mention for the rich literature written as response to the Councils' recommendations: Juan Guillermo Durán, *Monumenta catechetica hispanoamericana: (Siglos XVI-XVIII)*. Universidad Católica Argentina Santa María de los Buenos Aires, Facultad de Teología, 3

complementary sermons, on page 86 in another script: *Domenica in Quinquagesima* and one about Ash Wednesday, of unknown origin, probably written by Paraguayan Jesuits.

After this part follows another section, also with a collection of sermons (chapter titles in the annex). They correspond to the type of sermonary dedicated to various saints and their days, the sanctuary type. At the end, we find some notes in another hand probably by the first owners.

The question of authorship

We have no mention of author or translator at the title pages. B1 is a copy of the *Explicacion* by Yapuguay. The question of the authorship of parts of B2 can only be determined as far as the Acosta sermons and the Ripalda Catechism is concerned. However, we have no other mention of the translators for the Acosta model sermons.

The same is the case for the other sermons in Part 3. We haven't found a parallel version in some of the manuscript versions of sermonaries known to us, however, there is a clear tendency to treat the same Saints as in them. In the third part of B2 we find a "Father Anselmo" mentioned above one sermon in a very small note at the top of a page (p.159, *Sermon de San Ignacio*; that note is not found on the page at the beginning of the sermon). It may be an attribution, perhaps from memory, of one of the first readers or owners, maybe another Jesuit. We do not know who this Anselmo was, but the absence of personal author names is common in Jesuit sermons.

The only sermons the Jesuits attributed to an author/collaborator are the ones in the Jesuit prints of the *Yapuguay Sermones*, and in this case, the Jesuit and indigenous contribution is still to be investigated by further research. At that point, we can say that the authorship of an indigenous as Nicolás Yapuguay in collaboration with a Jesuit as Restivo is certainly intended to give as author/contributor/corrector the name of a renowned historical figure to inspire confidence in the faithful. These sermons were certainly supposed to be used in the *cofradías* or congregations and are often mentioned in the Jesuit inventories in the missions.⁸ We have to take in mind that every Jesuit mission had normally only two Jesuits for religious guidance, so they had to rely heavily on an indigenous élite of literate *administradores*, musicians⁹ and members of

vol. 1984-2007. The Acosta sermons can be found there in vol. 2, *Tabla del contenido* p.608, *Comentario* pp.601-612, *texto* pp. 617-741.

⁸ For more details, see Obermeier 2019b with detailed provenance information.

⁹ For the indigenous participation in music see: Porto (1954) and mainly based on manuscripts of the Jesuit José Cardiel and Preiss (1988).

cofradías for religious education of a population of usually thousands of indigenous.¹⁰

A small example of devotional practices

These manuscripts are valuable also because they give an insight in daily devotional practices.

After doctrine 40 in B1 and a "Doctrine 8" (of unknown origin, maybe copied from other manuscripts at hand) we have some personal notes in another hand with the subdivisions (we translate): Some exercises of Devotion. // Upon waking in the morning, Before going to bed, Upon entering the Church. We found one model or parallel text in the already mentioned manuscript collection British Library Add 21262, ed. in *Catecismos varios*, volume VI, original page, pp.245v-247v, here as part of the *Compendio de la Doctrina christiana para Niños*. Compuesto en lengua francesa por el R[everendo] P[adre] Francisco Pomeii (Pomey), de la Compañia de Jesús. Traducido en lengua Guaraní por el P. Christoval Altamirano de la misma Compañia. The structure of the chapters is in translation: When you wake up in the morning, Before going to bed, When entering the Church, When taking holy water, Being on your knees in front of the Blessed Sacrament, Before hearing Mass, When raising the Host [during consecration], When raising the Chalice, To the "Hostia postrera" [i.e.when the faithful are praying: *In manus tuas Domine commendo spiritum meum, redemisti me Domine Deus veritatis*], Before going to work, Before Eating, After Eating, When the Hail Mary is prayed, The Guardian Angel, At the sound of the Death knell, When the bells of All Souls sound, When you pass through the Cemetery, When you see a Holy cross. Some chapter subdivisions of that manuscript are lacking, which are "When taking holy water, Kneeling in front of the Blessed Sacrament", furthermore the version in B1 is not preserved in full. The fragmentary text of B1 ends with the chapter When entering in the church, London manuscript, numbered phrase No. 4. The full London text continues to

¹⁰ To indigenous literacy has been given a lot of attention in recent research, so we mention only a few contributions. After the groundbreaking work of Neumann (2005), see: Couchonnal / Wilde, (2014), Cerno / Obermeier (2013) the latter for the contribution of linguistics for our understanding.

p.250 in the original manuscript.¹¹ This small example shows how the Jesuits tried to change the devotional practice in a sort of continuous mental oration.

Early postjesuitical use of these manuscripts

Why have these manuscripts been conserved at all? All books and manuscripts from Jesuit libraries have been confiscated and sold some years after their exile in 1767 and many manuscripts are now lost. In our case, their conservation is probably due to the first owners, which also shows that they were in continuous devotional use even in a post-jesuitical era. In B2 we have an important providence note: Izidro Taropé // Mestre da musica // Pio Tatay // Izidro Taropé / Mestre da Musica do Povo de Santo / Angelo da guarda) on the front page. The mention of a reduction helps, even if it does not exclude that a first binding of separate texts from various missions was made later, perhaps in 1810, a date that is indicated on a piece of sheet cast later at the beginning of the manuscript (probably taken from an original cover sheet in poor conservation). At the bottom of p.138 in the same part, we have another owner mention of the same person: Katia marangatu / Izidro Taropé.

Very important is the mention that Izidro Taropé was a music teacher. According to the Preface to the reader (no pagination) of the Explicacion de el catecismo by Yapuguay, Yapuguay was also a musician. We recognize a pattern of use of these sermons and their public. Musicians had to be literate, as they had to accompany the chants during mass. They certainly were also frequently members of congregations and therefore read devotional texts and sermons in Guaraní during their exercises with other congregation members. B2 is the only manuscript, which gives in one provenance the profession of an indigenous *during the Jesuit time*. In other manuscripts, we sometimes have names of

¹¹ Another slightly different version of these devotional exercises in: Catechismos varios, a major Catechism by an anonymous author in vol. IV, pp.143v-146v., in a Chapter "Notice to spend the day in a christian way, and virtuously", p.140v., following. Probably these exercises had to be learned by heart during religious education at school and were common among the Guaraní. Daily orations were often recommended for instance in the last printed Guaraní text in colonial times, by Father Insaurrealde about the Buen uso del tempo (translation of the Guaraní title) 1759/60, vol. 2, pp.9-28, Joseph Insaurrealde, Ara poru agu^oiyey haba conico, quatia poromboe ha marângâtu [ó Buen uso del tiempo] ... 2 volumes, Madrid: J. Ibarra 1759-1760. In this book, the last to be printed in Guaraní in colonial times, we find some similar prayer, l.c., vol 2, pp.17-18, Al entrar de la iglesia, Tuparoque teique ramo, etc. Cf. the digitized version available at:

<https://archive.org/details/araporuaguyeyhab01insa/page/16/mode/2up>.

The Insaurrealde text was written in the 1720th at the latest (he died in 1730) and only published posthumously.

presbyters who used the manuscripts in post-jesuitical time; in a lot of texts we have marginal notes as in B1 and B2 of indigenous people and sometimes names added in margins by other hands in post-jesuitical times.¹² In one manuscript, for instance, with the title *Educacion cristiana* now at the John Carter Brown library in Providence we have the name of an administrator and his profession given in the manuscript.¹³

Our Izidro Taropé was certainly a Guaraní, the name Tarope-miri (miri = small) refers to a plant (Caá-apia in Tupi). Another important point is that the name of the reduction is given: Santo Angelo. From the context of a use of Portuguese forms “Mestre da muscia”, and “Povo de Santo Angelo” it can be deduced that it certainly was what today is in Brazil in Rio Grande do Sul the ex-Redução de Santo Ângelo founded by Father Diogo Haze (1706). It was the last reduction founded in Jesuit times; it has been destroyed, in the Guaraní war, being part of the famous Seven Towns of the Missions, or Sete Povos das Missões. Today the town is called Santo Ângelo.¹⁴

Wilhelm von Humboldt and Guaraní devotional manuscripts

This provenance from one of the so called seven towns also explains that the manuscript later came to light in Southern Brazil, most probably through investigations at the request of Humboldt who wanted current Guaraní material for his linguistic studies and was a friend of Olfers. We have letters from Humboldt to Olfers in which he sends a title list of the very rare books he needed for his comparative language studies in native American languages. Several letters in his correspondence with Olfers mention this request. During Olfers' time at the embassy in Lisbon in the beginning of the 1820s Humboldt thought that his friend might be able there to help him to get some rare prints or other linguistic documents from missionaries in the former colonies.¹⁵ When

¹² See Medan 2018 for Guaraní notes in a copy of Yapuguay's explicacion.

¹³ In the *Edvcacion Christiana:// y buena criança de los niños guaranis*, 1713, today in the John Carter Brown Library (signature 1-SIZE Codex / Ind / 45), digital version: <http://www.archive.org/> we find a presentation inscription on front pastedown “Año de 1790 me dio este libro el administrador de Sta. Lucia D[o]n Diego Antonio de Pxò. Fr. Miguel Guaxás (?)”.

¹⁴ For the history of these reducciones: “The seven Brazilian missions east of the Uruguay River—San Miguel, San Luis, San Juan Bautista, San Nicolás, San Lorenzo, San Ángel, and San Borja—lingered on for another decade. In 1828, Fructuoso Rivera invaded Brazilian territory during the extended struggle between Argentina and Brazil that ultimately led to the creation of the nation of Uruguay. Rivera depopulated the region and forced the remaining mission inhabitants to emigrate to Uruguay.” Sarreal (2014), pp.16/17.

¹⁵ The original letters of this correspondence have been formerly in the Staatsbibliothek Berlin, today in the Krakow Library. Wilhelm von Humboldt, Letter to Ignaz von Olfers, 06.11.1821 <https://wvh-briefe.bbaw.de/Brief?section=all&id=879>.

Olfers prepared for his second trip to Brazil, Wilhelm von Humboldt wrote to him again on the same topic on 26 of July 1826.¹⁶ Olfers at least tried to attend on Humboldt's requests, as we see in his reply to Wilhelm von Humboldt, written Rio de Janeiro on October 23, 1827. As an annex to that letter is added a list from Humboldt of the books he didn't have access to and asked him to get for him. Olfers sent it to some other acquaintances who might help him in his quest.¹⁷

Humboldt tried to get all available missionary linguistic documents even through contacts with the former Jesuit Lorenzo Hervás¹⁸, exiled in Italy with his coreligionaries. We have a lot of manuscript grammars of South American indigenous languages which were written at the request of the polyhistorian Hervás working on a language typology.¹⁹

Wilhelm von Humboldt had also interest in the rare "temporal" (i.e. on secular topics) documents as, for instance, two Guaraní Cabildo letters his brother Alexander copied for him in Paris.²⁰

We do not know the date of the purchase of B1 and B2 in Brasil, but as we know the moment when Olfers stayed there for the second time, it may correspond to the historical phase in which in 1828 the invasion of Fructuoso Rivera destroyed the remains of the seven peoples definitively. Part of the indigenous population and the Brazilians who had collaborated came to Brazil. The indigenous people took everything that had any value with them; the towns were destroyed, with the exception of São Borja. Rivera founded Bella Unión, officially called Santa Rosa del Cuareim. Even this colony had to suffer during the domination of Fructuoso Rivera and was soon depopulated. Some Brazilians returned to their country, other Guaraní groups went to Entre Ríos, an Argentine province.

¹⁶ <https://wvh-briefe.bbaw.de/Brief?section=all&id=881>

¹⁷ <https://wvh-briefe.bbaw.de/439?view=leser>.

¹⁸ For Humboldt's relation to Hervás see Battlori (1951/1966). For Hervás see in general Obermeier (2019a).

¹⁹ In his encyclopedic work *Idea dell'uomo*, Vol. 17, *Catalogo delle lingue conosciute e notizia della loro affinità e diversità*. Cesena, Gregorio Biasini, 1784, extended version in Spanish as: *Catálogo de las lenguas de las Naciones conocidas y numeración, división y clases de éstas, según la diversidad de sus idiomas y dialectos*. Madrid, Imprenta de la Administración del Real Arbitrio de Beneficencia, 6 vol. 1800-1805.

²⁰ We could identify the originals of these letters in a manuscript called *Reorganizacion y plan de seguridad exterior de las muy interesantes colonias orientales del rio Paraguay ó de la Plata, etc.*, Manuscrit Espagnol 170-171, compiled by Miguel Lastarria y Villanueva (Arequipa, Peru 1759 - Sevilla, 1817) and now in one copy in the National library of Paris. For these letters see Ringmacher, (2014). In this case, we also have no evidence that Humboldt used his brother's copy for his own research even if he kept the copies. For these letters see: Ringmacher M. (2014).

Conclusion

Our brief contribution has given evidence that the research about devotional manuscripts from the reducciones is still at a beginning. We have shown that a detailed description of the manuscript gives evidence of which orisons and which hybrid text types were used in devotional practices, most probably in congregations. The research on this topic up to now has been focusing on some texts, such as the easily available Ruiz de Montoya Catechism and linguistic books, as they are available in print. To a lesser extent, the Yapuguay prints have been always mentioned, but there is no thorough research about them. However, the texts in use were a lot more, ranging from translations of model sermons as the ones Acosta had written for Chile to original sermons written on place in the Paraguayan Jesuit province and conserved as manuscripts. The last devotional text by the Jesuit father José Insaurralde was published posthumously in 1759/60 in Madrid and has also found little research interest up to now.²¹ All of these documents help us for a better understanding of indigenous devotional practices and their readings in the Jesuit missions.

The provenance history in our case is also very important, to see the interest of collectors as Olfers at the request of linguists as Wilhelm von Humboldt as an evidence for the beginning research interest in the 19th century. Olfers probably kept the precious original manuscripts after having shown them to Humboldt, who obviously wasn't able to understand these documents, as a souvenir of his stays in Brazil in his personal library.

²¹ See for a beginning: Boidin/ Cerno / Vega (2020).

Annex**Manuscript amer. 12, = B1**

Yapuguay, Nicolas: „Explicación de el Catechismo en lengua guaraní”

<https://jbc.bj.uj.edu.pl/dlibra/publication/492020/edition/466364>

18th century, binding 19th century

Preliminary sheet with contemporary notes in Guaraní.

Doctrina primera [fragmentary at the beginning] until Doctrina 40, con Exercicios.

= the First part of the Explicacion of Yapuguay is complete.

Small annexes by other hands “Doctrina 8 with Algunos ejercicios de Deuocion”. (see our analyse above)

Ms amer. 13 = B2

Digital: Biblioteka Jagiellońska, Krakow, Polonia, Sermones i inne teksty m. in. w jęz. hiszpańskim

<https://jbc.bj.uj.edu.pl/dlibra/publication/492011/edition/466350>

18th century

Binding: 19th century

Preliminary page with fragment of a lost original page: “16 de Maio 1810”

Frontispice:

Izidro Taropé, Povo de Santo Angelo, today Brazil, Rio Grande do Sul ex-Redução São Miguel Arcanjo

Acquisition date of the Berlin library 1897, Frontpage: Izidro Taropé // Mestre da musica// Pio Tatay // Izidro Taropé / Mestre da Musica do Povo de Santo/ Angelo da guarda.

[Parte I] Catecismo

“Doctrina Christiana“, copied from a version of the *Exposición breve de la Doctrina Christiana* por el P. M.G. de Ripalda, emendado y traducido en guarani por Francisco Martinez (facsimile after a manuscript version in British Library BL Add 21262 in: *Catecismos Vários*, vol. III, ed. São Paulo, 1954).

A few lacunae (Doctrina 11- Doctrina 16). Some errors in the chapter numbers compared to BL Add 21262 (ed. citada), original pages: pp.64 r-80v. The London Ripalda translation is dated “recogidas en la Doctrina de S. Nicolas. Año 1716”.

P. 52-54 added: Some prayers “Actos” as Credo, Doleo, Spero, Amo, Fiat voluntas tua, to be compared, for instance, with the *Officium Rakocianum sive Selecta pietatis exercitia cultui divino, in quo continentur Exercitia ordinaria Hominis Christiani. Sodalibus sub titulo Beatae Virginis Mariae ab Angelo salatatae in caesares regioque societatis collegio Zagrabiata congregatis, pro Xenio oblatum, Commendatio Moribundi, Zagrabiae/Zagreb 1737*, p.312. Other parallel version: *Doctrina Christiana*, in: *Catecismos Vários* vol. I, pp.15r-18r como “Actos de las Virtudes Theologales necesarias para la Salvacion, with the parts : Actos de Fe, y sus motivos, p.15r, Tupã rerobia haba, p.15v, Actos de Esperanza, y sus motivos p.15v, Ñandeyara tupã rehe Yerobiaha, p.16r, Actos del Amor e Dios, y sus motivos p.16 v, Tupã raihu haba, p.17r, Motivos para el dolor y contricion de los pecados, p.17r, Angaypa mboacĩ catu hàba, p.17v.

p.55 added: Tupareco/La Doctrina. Blanks 56-58

[Part II] Sermones translations

p.59 marginalia: Del P.^e Acosta. Sermon 1 en que se declaran los primeros presupuestos de la fe [...]

Sermon 1-7 are from the *Tercero catecismo y exposicion de la Doctrina Christiana*, por Sermones Los Reyes [i.e., Lima]: Printer: Antonio Ricardo, 1585, in a Guaraní translation by an unknown translator.

At the end two added sermons by unknown authors in another hand: p.86 *Domenica in Quinquagesima*, p.87: Ash Wednesday.

[Part III] Sermones (type of a sanctuary)

Another handwriting. p.89: In conceptione Beatae Mariae. // p.94: Nativitas beatae Mariae. // p.101: Presentacion de N. Señora // p.106: Annunciation// p.111 Purificacion // p.118 [cancelled:] Purificacion [corrected in:]: Assumpcion // p.126 S. Maria ad Nives. // p.136-138 blank // p.138: Provenance note : Katia marangatu / Izidro Taropé // p.139 San Miguel Archangel // p.155 San Ignacio. In this sermon mention of one “Padre Anselmo” in a small note on top of page 159 // p.162 San Francisco Xavier. // p.69. Sancti Francisci Borgiae. // p.179 San Ludovici Gonzagae.// p.185 San Nicolas. // p.193 San Carlos. // p.203 Sancti Martyres Paulo Diego y Juan [i.e.Martires del Japón]. // p.209 Santa Ana. Fragmentary at the end.

Last numbered pages 216: Later notes: João Nandura [Amen Jesus / Amen Jesus], maybe another owner, or an exercise in writing a name, on p.217, small paper fragments from a destroyed page, we only mention the note: “Armaria”, evidently the place where the manuscript was held in the Jesuit mission library.

Literature

Manuscripts

For the Berlin manuscripts see the description above.

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